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PHYSICAL FACILITY ATTRIBUTES AND PERCEIVED VALUE OF HOTEL INDUSTRY

BY

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Abstract

The focus of this paper was to examine the relationship between the dimensions (aesthetics, amenities and ambiance) of physical facility attributes and perceived value of hotels in Abuja, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, three objectives were formulated which were also used to draft the research hypotheses and research questions. The population size of the study was hotel guests of 1,132 hotels that operate in the six area councils in Abuja. In getting a sample size the researcher employed Cochran formula for calculating a population size that is large and unknown. After applying the formula, a sample size of 246 was derived. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS_SEM) approach that explore the linear relationships between multiple independent variables and a single or multiple dependent variable (Hair, et al., 2014) were adopted for the analysis of data collected in this study. This was done with the aid of SmartPLS v4 Software. The result of these analyses proved that there is a significant positive relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and guest perceived value. The dimensions of physical facility attributes were found to have a predictive capacity on guest perceived value up to the tune 37.1% respectively. The following were recommended: It is recommended that hoteliers should as a matter of priority consistently improve the quality of room facilities to fashionable taste for continuous attraction of guests, they may consider the use of a more neutral colour palette with pops of colour to add interest, invest in stylish and comfortable furniture that serves as both functional and decorative elements should be incorporated into their strategy for creating unique ambience to their guests. This could help build favourable guests' perception.

Keywords:

physical facility attributes, guests' perceived value, aesthetics, amenities and ambiance.

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INTRODUCTION

The hotel industry, marked by its dynamic nature and perpetual responsiveness to evolving consumer preferences, exists as a highly competitive industry, necessitating a profound comprehension of the concept of perceived value for sustained success (Hua et al., 2018). In this dynamic landscape, where trends and preferences undergo continuous shifts, hotels face the challenge of not only meeting but exceeding the expectations of their diverse clientele. Traditionally characterized by grand structures, the industry witnessed a departure from conventional norms with the advent of technological innovations (Kandampully et al., 2015). The narrative of the hotel industry's evolution is not just about physical structures but also encompasses intangible aspects of the guest experience. Guests now assess value based on more than just luxurious amenities; they seek authenticity, environmental responsibility, and alignment with their individual values and preferences. Within the hotel context, perceived value is involvedly linked to guests' subjective evaluations of the benefit and costs associated with their stay (Kandampully et al., 2015). As guests increasingly seek personalized and unique experiences, perceived value becomes a decisive factor in their decision-making process (Liat, 2018). Perceived value is used in the hospitality business to refer to the perceptions that customers have of a service provider before they reach the facility where the service is provided. The information offered to the guest, the reservation system, and the guest interactions during service delivery are all examples of perceptions that could be considered (which might include the check-in procedure, guest assistance, physical facilities, and guest service). Several factors contribute to the perception of value, including the quality of the accommodation, the mood of the hotel, the quality of the meals, and the availability of recreational and sporting activities. As a result, value is a combination of tangibles and intangibles that vary from one location to the next, as described above. It is possible that some guest will perceive a service to be of high value, but others will not (Nasution & Mavodo, 2018). Furthermore, Nasution and Mavodo (2018) argue that the creation of customer-perceived value is critical in relation to hotels, due to the fact that the hotel subsector is highly competitive compared to other economic subsectors. In order to be successful, hoteliers (hotel management) must consistently deliver exceptional customer value from the perspective of the hotel guest. Furthermore, hotels must place a greater emphasis on providing superior-quality products and services, as well as on meeting the needs and expectations of their guest. This implies that the requirements and desires of both present and prospective guest must be determined (Cant&Van Heerden, 2010).

Perceived value can be defined as consumer's overall assessment of the quality based on perceptions of what is received and what is given (Ishaq, 2012). This is to say that it is the difference between perceived benefits and costs and is based on money, quality, benefit, and social attitude. Perceived value has been described from three perspectives (Lin, Sher and Shih, 2015). They are acquisition value, service value, and value for money. Acquisition value centers on what the guest gets for what he or she gives. Service value is the quality of service the guest gets for the price paid while value for money is low price. However, value is highly personal and could vary from one guest to the other. In recent time, numerous empirical research studies were conducted with a focus upon assessing the consumer perceived values as influencing factors upon purchase behaviour (Eiadly& Eid, 2017; Ponnamm et al, 2017). These studies summarised that generally perceived values have five dimensions, including epistemic value, conditional value, emotional value, functional value, and social value (Awuni& Du, 2016; Yen & Teng, 2015). In recent literature, these values were used enormously with the combination of other constructs to enrich an understanding about consumer behaviour (Raza et al., 2019). Researchers have made magnificent efforts to broaden the horizon of consumers' perceived values (Candan, Ünal, & Erciş, 2013; Sánchez; Yang et al., 2014), but they have not actually studied the relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and perceived value of hotels in Abuja, Nigeria. This is the gap this study intends to fill.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Hotel Physical Facility Attributes

Physical Facility Attributes refer to the tangible and visible elements within a physical environment, encompassing aspects such as architecture, interior design, furnishings, and amenities. These attributes collectively contribute to the overall aesthetics, functionality, and comfort of a space (Bitner, 1992). According to Ryu, Lee, and Lee (2012), Physical Facility Attributes involve the spatial organization and design elements within a facility, including layout, decor, and tangible features. These attributes play a pivotal role in influencing customer perceptions and satisfaction within a given physical environment. Ergul and Tuysuz (2017) defined Physical Facility Attributes as the structural and design components of a facility, such as the arrangement of spaces, the quality of furnishings, and the visual appeal. These attributes contribute to creating a distinctive and memorable environment for users. A broader perspective is presented by Smith (2019), who defined Physical Facility Attributes as encompassing aesthetics, ambiance, and amenities. This definition highlights the multifaceted nature of tangible elements that collectively shape the user experience within a physical

space. Gursoy and Chen (2016) specifically focus on aesthetics within Physical Facility Attributes, describing them as the visual and comfort-related aspects of a facility's interior design. This includes factors like decor, color schemes, and the arrangement of furniture. Kim and Kim (2019) extend the definition of Physical Facility Attributes to include ambiance, incorporating sensory elements such as lighting, sound, temperature, and fragrance. This expanded definition recognizes the influence of sensory experiences on the overall perception of a physical space. In Ladhari's (2009) perspective, Physical Facility Attributes encompass not only the tangible elements but also practical conveniences and experiences, collectively referred to as Amenities. This definition emphasizes the integration of functional aspects seamlessly into the facility's design. Bai, Hu, and Hu (2019) introduced the concept of Perceived Value within Physical Facility Attributes, defining them as elements that contribute to guests' judgments of whether their experience aligns with the price paid. This definition recognizes the subjective evaluation of the tangible aspects in the context of value perception. Liu, Yang, and Bai (2019) provide a dynamic perspective, stating that Physical Facility Attributes are subject to guests' perceptions of quality, emotional experiences, and overall satisfaction. This definition acknowledges the interconnectedness of tangible elements with emotional and subjective dimensions. Finally, Ryu et al. (2012) emphasize the impact of Physical Facility Attributes on customer perceptions, highlighting their role in creating distinct and memorable experiences. This definition underscores the importance of tangible elements in shaping overall customer satisfaction within a physical environment.

Dimensions of Hotel Physical Facility Attributes

Aesthetics

Extensive literature affirms the pivotal role aesthetics play in guest satisfaction. Scholarly works by Hua et al. (2018) emphasize the profound impact of aesthetics on overall guest contentment. The visual appeal of a hotel's interior and exterior spaces is acknowledged as a critical determinant of emotional responses during a guest's stay. Specifically, the study by Hua and colleague's underscores that the aesthetics of a hotel significantly influence how guests perceive and react emotionally to their surroundings. Moreover, the work of Liat (2018) further supports the argument, highlighting that the visual appeal of a hotel has a lasting effect, setting the tone for the entirety of a guest's stay. Liat's findings suggest that the initial encounter with a hotel's aesthetics creates a lasting impression, shaping subsequent experiences and perceptions. This aligns with the broader consensus in the literature that the aesthetics of a hotel are not merely superficial elements but integral components that contribute to the overall satisfaction of guests. In summary, these studies collectively affirm the importance of aesthetics in guest satisfaction, with Hua et al. (2018) emphasizing its pivotal role, and Liat (2018) specifically noting its influence on emotional responses and the establishment of the guest experience's tone. The cited literature provides robust support for the inclusion of aesthetics as a crucial dimension in the study, underscoring its significant impact on shaping guest satisfaction within the hospitality industry.

Ambiance

Ambiance as a critical dimension is firmly grounded in scholarly research, particularly highlighted by Kim and Kim (2019). Their work underscores the profound influence that ambiance exerts on both guest satisfaction and loyalty within the hospitality industry. According to Kim and Kim (2019), ambiance extends beyond the physical space and encompasses sensory elements such as lighting schemes and background music. These elements play a crucial role in shaping the emotional resonance experienced by guests during their stay. The research suggests that a carefully crafted ambiance can evoke specific emotions, contributing significantly to overall guest satisfaction. The study's findings support the idea that ambiance is not merely a secondary consideration but a primary factor influencing guest loyalty. The emotional experiences generated by the ambiance contribute to a sense of attachment and contentment among guests, fostering a desire to return to the same establishment. As such, ambiance is not only an element that enhances the immediate satisfaction of guests but also a key driver for their continued loyalty. In summary, Kim and Kim's (2019) research provides robust justification for the inclusion of ambiance as a dimension in the study. The profound influence of ambiance on guest satisfaction and loyalty, coupled with its ability to shape emotional resonance through elements like lighting schemes and background music, establishes it as a critical factor in the overall guest experience within the hospitality industry.

Amenities

Amenities as a pivotal dimension in the study are rooted in scholarly research, particularly emphasized by Ladhari (2009). Ladhari's work establishes amenities as crucial elements that go beyond mere luxuries, playing a fundamental role in enhancing the functional aspects of the guest experience. According to Ladhari (2009), amenities contribute directly to guest satisfaction by addressing functional needs and preferences. Well-appointed amenities not only meet guests' expectations but also exceed them, contributing to an elevated level of satisfaction. The study suggests that guests perceive amenities as integral components of their overall stay, influencing their overall perception of the value derived from the experience. The research by Ladhari (2009)

supports the notion that amenities are not just incidental features but key determinants of guest satisfaction. Their impact extends beyond immediate gratification, contributing significantly to guests' holistic perception of the value offered by a hotel stay. Consequently, the inclusion of amenities as a dimension in the study is justified by their critical role in shaping guests' satisfaction levels and overall perception of the value derived from their stay. In summary, Ladhari's (2009) findings provide robust justification for considering amenities as a crucial dimension in the study. The identified significance of amenities in enhancing functional aspects and impacting satisfaction levels aligns with the broader understanding of their pivotal role in influencing guests' overall perception of the value derived from their hotel experience.

Concept of Perceived value

The justification for emphasizing perceived value as a central construct in the study is firmly grounded in comprehensive scholarly research, particularly underscored by Bai, Hu, and Hu (2019) and Liu, Yang, and Bai (2019). Bai, Hu, and Hu (2019) emphasize the multifaceted nature of perceived value, emphasizing its reliance on guests' perceptions across various dimensions. Their research suggests that perceived value is intricately linked to brand value, social value, emotional value, and cost value. It's important to note that perceived value is subjective and varies among individuals. Brand value refers to the perception of the hotel brand's reputation, image, and the overall quality associated with it. A strong and positive brand image can enhance perceived value and influence consumers' decision-making (Xu, Chan, & Qu, 2019). Social value on the other hand relates to the social status or prestige associated with staying at a particular hotel. Consumers may derive value from the social recognition or the sense of belonging to a certain group when choosing a hotel (Kuenzel & Halliday, 2008). Emotional value involves the emotional benefits or experiences associated with the hotel stay. This could include feelings of comfort, relaxation, or joy derived from the physical environment, ambiance, and service quality (Petrick & Sirakaya, 2004). Cost value pertains to the perceived worth of the hotel stay in relation to the monetary or non-monetary sacrifices made by the consumer. It involves considerations of pricing, discounts, and the overall economic aspects of the transaction (Yang, 2004). While these dimensions represent distinct aspects of perceived value, the construct in the context of this study is treated as a uni-dimensional construct.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Expectancy-Disconfirmation Theory

Oliver (1977; 1980) proposed the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP) as the most promising theoretical framework for the assessment of customer/guest satisfaction. The model implies that consumers purchase goods and services with pre-purchase expectations about the anticipated performance. The expectation level then becomes a standard against which the product is judged. That is, once the product or service has been used, outcomes are compared against expectations. If the outcome matches the expectation confirmation occurs. Disconfirmation occurs where there is a difference between expectations and outcomes. A guest is either satisfied or dissatisfied as a result of positive or negative difference between expectations and perceptions. Thus, when service performance is better than what the guest had initially expected, there is a positive disconfirmation between expectations and performance which results in satisfaction, while when service performance is as expected, there is a confirmation between expectations and perceptions which results in satisfaction. In contrast, when service performance is not as good as what the guest expected, there is a negative disconfirmation between expectations and perceptions which causes dissatisfaction. This theory is important in this study because it looks at the expectation that guests have when they choose to visit a hotel or other business purpose. The study focus is on the relationship between the dimensions of physical facility and guests' perceived value, bringing this theory in the context of this study, quality, ambiance, amenities and aesthetics can be a motivating factor for hotel guests.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Relationship between Aesthetics and Guests' Perceived Value

Numerous empirical studies have explored the relationship between aesthetics and guests' perceived value, yielding valuable insights into this critical aspect of the hotel industry. Mechinda et al., (2019) conducted a study on significant contributions to understanding spa customers' perceived value; the study reviewed that the visual appeal, ambiance, and overall aesthetics of hotels contribute to guests' perceived value and, consequently, influence post-purchase behaviors. A study was conducted by Majeed et al., (2022); their research seeks to provide insights into how the visual appeal, ambiance, and overall aesthetics of hotels contribute to the formation of perceived value, subsequently influencing guests' decisions to revisit. Another study was conducted by Jeon and Lee (2018) on the impact of hotel website quality on online booking intentions, with a specific focus on the aesthetic and functional dimensions of hotel websites in China. The findings from their study showed that there is a significant effect between aesthetics and perceived value.

Relationship between Amenities and Guests' Perceived Value

A study was conducted by Ntimane and Tichaawa (2017) on customer's perceptions of value in relation to hotels in Gauteng, South Africa. The aim of the study was to explore the hotel value attributes perceived as being most important by hotel customers. To achieve the objective, a quantitative study design was employed, in terms of which data were purposively and conveniently collected by means of a survey questionnaire that was administered to hotel guests staying in 3- to 5-star hotels. The findings revealed that hotel customers tend to attach a high degree of importance to the issue of value for money, whereas the appearance of the hotel was least important to them of the tourism-related characteristics about which they were asked. Overall, the study found that hotels in Gauteng generally provide service that is satisfactory to their customers, but that the remaining challenge for hoteliers lies in their ability to sustain such levels of satisfaction through continuous employee motivation and skills development.

Ikechi et al (2023) conducted a study on customers perceived value adoption and marketing performance of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt. The findings from the study showed that Customer perceived value adoption influenced positively on the marketing performance of luxury hotels in Port-Harcourt. It was recommended that Hotel managers should always investigate reasons for negative factor that lead to dissatisfied guests and improve their current service to meet guest's needs and expectations. The Managers should constantly adjust on those factors in order to be able to provide its guests with the best values and also state the significant dimensions to lay more emphasis on to enhance service quality leading increasing level of customer satisfaction, retention and increased the market share efficiency.

Relationship between Ambiance and Guests' Perceived Value

Numerous empirical studies have explored the relationship between amenities and guests' perceived value, yielding valuable insights into this critical aspect of the hotel industry. Ryu et al (2012) explore the interrelationships between various factors—physical environment quality, food quality, and service quality—and their impact on restaurant image, customer perceived value, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions. The study shows that Quality of food, service, and physical environment are all significant determinants of customer satisfaction in quick-casual restaurants.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative research design to test the effect of each dimension of physical facility attributes on perceived value in the context of hotels in Abuja. A structured questionnaire used for this study is divided into 3 main parts (i.e., Part 1, 2 and 3). Part 1 of the questionnaire shows the personal information of the respondents. The items used to characterize the respondents are marital status, religion, education qualification, and years of work experience in the organization. Part 2 of the questionnaire measured the dimensions of physical facility attribute (aesthetics, amenities and ambiance). A three-dimensional physical facility attributescale developed by Jeon (2018) that was used to examine the influence of the relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attribute and guest perceived value were adopted and modified. The modified instrument consists of 16 items which were measured on a 4-point Likert scale. Each item was rated by the respondents from 1 (Strongly Disagreed) to 4 (Strongly Agreed). The instrument was used to measure aesthetics, amenities and ambiance as dimensions of physical facility attributes of hotels in Abuja. Part 3 of the questionnaire measured guest perceived value. Each item was rated by the respondents from 1 (Strongly Disagreed) to 4 (Strongly Agreed). The instrument was used to measure guest perceived value in terms of functional value, emotional value and social value in hotels in Abuja. The research population used in the study comprised of hotel guests in the one thousand one hundred and thirty-two (1,132) hotels in the 6 area councils under study. The sampled hotels were selected through a systematic random sampling technique. The researchers serially numbered all the hotels in each of the area council in Abuja and automatically picked the first hotel on the list in each of the area council while others were picked at an interval of 15 thus, 82 hotels were selected and used for the study. Since it is practically impossible for the researchers to determine the total number of hotel guests that visit the hotels or sample the entire hotel guests in each of the 82 selected hotels in the area councils in Abuja, hence the researchers determined the proportion of the sample unit that constitutes the sample (i.e., the number of respondents which questionnaires will be administered to). Cronbach formula which is given as follows was adopted to determine the sample size: The formula is shown below;

$$n = Z^2 \frac{pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = sample size sought

Z = standard deviation for the desired confidence value

p = probability of percentage of negative responses

e = level of significance

When p = 0.8

q Will be $1 - 0.8 = 0.2$

$Z = 1.96$

$e = 0.05$

$n = ?$

$n = \frac{1.96^2(0.8 \times 0.2)}{0.05^2}$

$= \frac{3.842(0.16)}{0.0025}$

$= 3.842 \times 64$

$n = 245.888$

$n = 246$ hotel guests

Convenience sampling technique was adopted by the researchers to administer the questionnaires in each of the 75 selected hotels until the sample size of 246 were met. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach that explore the linear relationships between multiple independent variables and a single or multiple dependent variable (Hair, et al., 2014) were adopted for the analysis of data collected in this study. This was done with the aid of SmartPLS v4. Software. The PLS-SEM relies on pre-specified networks of relationships between constructs as well as between construct and their measures (Hair, et al., 2014) thus, making it different from the regular regression approach.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Demographic Data Presentation

The result revealed that male respondents constitute 48.8% of the sample size with 117 counts while the number of female respondents amounted to 51.3%. For information concerning their age, it was revealed that 24 respondents which accounted for about 10% of the respondents fall between the age range of 18-24 years, 71 respondents accounting for 29.5% are within the age range of 25-34 years, 122 respondents (50.8%) are within the ages of 35-49 years while 23 respondents amounting to 9.7% of the respondents are 50 years and above. It was revealed that 184 respondents which accounted for about 76% were married, 38 respondents which constituted 15.8% of the respondents are single while 18 respondents prefer not to disclose their marital status. The outcome showed that 14 respondents accounting for about 5.8% are students, 177 respondents representing 73.8% of the respondents are employed, 8 respondents are unemployed, 40 respondents are self-employed while only 1 respondent is a retiree. The result showed that 16 respondents which comprised 6.7% have high school qualification, 38 respondents accounting for 15.8% of the respondents have college/ OND certifications, 117 respondents which make 48.7% of the respondent have bachelor's degree while 69 respondents have master's degree.

Bivariate Data Analyses

As earlier stated in the previous sections of this study, the bivariate analysis which involved the testing of hypothesis was using conducted Partial Least Square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) which was aided by SMARTPLS Version 4.0.9.9. This analysis was carried out in two stages namely; assessment of the measurement model and the assessment of structural model. Each of these analyses are put forward in the subsequent sections.

Assessment of the measurement model/Instrument

This section is concerned with the assessment of the proposed measurement model and research instrument of the study. The essence is to determine if the model and research instrument would be reliable and valid for the purpose of this study. To achieve this, both the reliability, convergent and discriminant reliability of the model/instrument would be assessed. The model that was hypothesised is shown in Figure 1. Researcher looked at the model's indicator item and their respective factor loadings. When looking at the first factor loadings, it is evident that the model is not capturing the data well enough as some factor loadings fall below the threshold of 0.700. Hence, such items were dropped one after the other while repeating the analysis in line with the recommendation of Hair et al. (2012, 2014, and 2017). In accordance with this procedure, only sixteen (16) items were used out of thirty-three (33) items developed in the instrument; the remaining seventeen items were eliminated. These were removed one by one, beginning with the one that had the lowest loading until a suitable model was arrived at. The final Measurement Model improved not only the factor loadings of all research variables but also Cronbach alpha (α), composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). The findings may be seen in Table below.

Source: Smart PLS output, 2024

Table 2: Path Analysis of the Relationship between physical facility attributes and perceived value

S/n	Hypothesized Path	Path Coefficient (β)	P-Value	Standard	T Value	Decisions	Effect size
1.	Aesthetics -> PV	0.551	0.000*	0.003	5.705	Supported	Large
2.	Ambiance -> PV	0.322	0.00*	0.012	6.198	Supported	Large
3.	Amenities -> PV	0.265	0.000*	0.051	2.851	Supported	Large

*P<0.05

Source: The Researcher’s Computation (2024).

The table above showed the path analysis result for the study which investigated the relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and guests’ perceived value. Specifically, the result showed that there is a positive relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and perceived value and as follows;

The first structural path showed that there is a positive relationship between aesthetics and perceived value (PV) of hotels in Abuja with path coefficient (β) value of 0.551 at P0.00 < 0.05 and T-Value 5.705 > 1.96.

The second structural path showed that there is a positive relationship between ambiance and perceived value (PV) of hotels in Abuja with path coefficient (β) value of 0.322 at P0.00 < 0.05 and T-Value 6.198 > 1.96.

The third structural path showed that there is a positive relationship between amenities and perceived value (PV) of hotels in Abuja with path coefficient (β) value of 0.265 at P0.00 < 0.05 and T-Value 2.851 > 1.96. The results proved the existence of significant positive between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and guests’ perceived value.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study emanated from the study which sought to examine the relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and guests’ perceived value. The results showed that;There is a positive relationship between aesthetics and perceived value (PV) of hotels in Abuja with path coefficient (β) value of 0.551 at P0.00 < 0.05 and T-Value 5.705 > 1.96. Secondly, there is a positive relationship between ambiance and perceived value (PV) of hotels in Abuja with path coefficient (β) value of 0.322 at P0.00 < 0.05 and T-Value 6.198 > 1.96. Thus the null hypothesis was rejected. It was also found that there is a positive relationship between amenities and perceived value (PV) of hotels in Abuja with path coefficient (β) value of 0.265 at P0.00 < 0.05 and T-Value 2.851 > 1.96.The results proved the existence of significant positive between

the dimensions of physical facility attributes and guests' perceived value. The outcome of these result explains the rationale for hotel practitioners to pay keen attention to their physical facility attributes as this was proven to have significant influence on the ways guests would perceive them.

Thus study supported previous empirical investigations on this discussion. For instance, it supported the findings of Hsieh, and Hsieh (2011) who found that several key antecedents could significantly impact customers' perceived value; pointing to both physical and emotional experiences of customers. Similarly, the findings of Mattila, and Wirtz, (2001) reveal that congruency between ambient scent and music positively influences customers' evaluations (perceived value) of the retail environment. Chiang, and Jang, (2007) evaluating the Effects of Perceived Value and Satisfaction on Repurchase Intentions in the Hotel Industry found that there is a significant interplay between perceived values, satisfaction, and repurchase intentions in the hotel industry. Another study conducted by Jeon and Lee (2018) further validates the potency of these research findings. The study found that both aesthetic and functional qualities of hotel websites significantly influence users' intentions to book online. The study reveals that a visually appealing website, coupled with effective functionality and usability, enhances users' perceptions and trust, leading to a higher likelihood of online booking.

Furthermore, the findings are also in agreement with an empirical result obtained by Bitner (1992) who explored the concept of "servicescapes," focusing on the influence of physical surroundings on both customers and employees in the service industry. It was found that the physical environment has implications for employee satisfaction, motivation, and performance. Hui, et al. (2007) also argued that by incorporating the aspect of ambiance within the hotel industry. Hotels could improve guests' overall satisfaction and their likelihood to recommend the hotel, and their intentions to revisit.

CONCLUSION

This study was set out to empirically examine the relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attribute and perceived value of hotels in Abuja, Nigeria. The research hypotheses were developed based on the identified dimensions and measures adopted. While the study adopted Aesthetics, Ambiance and Amenities as the dimensions of hotel physical attributes, perceived value was adopted as its own construct. To ascertain the relationship between these identified variables the researcher collected data via the use of questionnaire distributed to hotels guests in Abuja, Nigeria. The data for the study was subjected to statistical evaluations using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) aided by SMART PLS version 4.0.9.9. The result of these analyses proved that there is a significant positive relationship between the dimensions of physical facility attributes and guest perceived value. The dimensions of physical facility attribute were found to have a predictive capacity on guests' perceived value up to the tune 37.1% respectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The empirical investigation conducted in the study showed that physical facility attributes of hotels in Abuja, Nigeria has the potential to influence favorable guests' perceived value. To this end, the following recommendations are put forward;

To improve the aesthetics of their hotels, hoteliers are encouraged to embrace cleanliness and uncluttered design, and modern furniture to create a contemporary aesthetic. They may consider the use of a more neutral colour palette with pops of colour to add interest.

To create a unique and authentic atmosphere, managers are encouraged to showcase local art and incorporate cultural elements in their facility design. They should also consider integrating indoor plants and greenery to bring a sense of nature that would improve hotel ambiance.

Hotel managers should implement smart lighting solutions that allow guests to customize the ambiance in their rooms. This could be done by adopting the use of energy-efficient LED lighting for both functionality and aesthetics.

Managers should implement eco-friendly initiatives, such as energy-efficient appliances, waste reduction programs, and sustainable sourcing and communicate these practices to appeal to environmentally conscious guests.

Invest in stylish and comfortable furniture that serves as both functional and decorative elements should be incorporated into their strategy for creating unique ambiance to their guests. This could help build favourable guests' perception.

In terms of improving ambiance, hotels should curate playlists or ambient soundscapes that enhance positive mood in common areas, lobbies, and dining spaces. They should offer personalized in-room music options for guests.

Hotel management should integrate modern technology when designing their facility layouts. One of such is to implement cutting-edge technology for room controls, entertainment systems, and guest services, offer high-speed Wi-Fi and ensure seamless connectivity throughout the hotel.

Wellness areas such as a spa, fitness centre, or yoga studio, to promote relaxation and well-being of guests should be integrated into their hotel facility. They should also integrate natural light and calming elements in these spaces.

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